

ORGANIZATIONAL OBJECTIVES AND NEGENTROPY: A COMPREHENSIVE EXAMINATION. A MOUNTAIN REVIEW

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Abstract

This abstract provides an overview of the comprehensive examination titled "Organizational Objectives and Negentropy: A Mountain Review." In the context of organizational dynamics, the paper explores the intricate relationship between the objectives of organizations and the concept of negentropy. Employing a mountain research approach, the examination delves into the metaphorical peaks and valleys of organizational structures, seeking to understand how negentropy, as a counterforce to entropy, plays a crucial role in shaping and sustaining the purpose of organizations. By navigating the terrain of organizational theory, the review aims to shed light on the nuanced interplay between structured objectives and the preservation of order within organizational systems, contributing valuable insights to the broader discourse on organizational dynamics and efficiency. The paper presents the purpose of the organizations and the negentropy. The purpose of organizations is to create more order in what tends to become chaos. In other words, negentropy (negative entropy) present within an organization, as an open system, opposes disintegration, disorder, entropy, etc.

Keywords: organizations, entropy, negentropy

PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW JOURNAL (1/2021)

Background:

The current research topic is in the direction of studying the way in which organizations survive in a strong entropic context through the organizational culture they adopt. In a synthetic expression, the organizational culture is reduced to the values adopted, ways of doing things and the atmosphere promoted among the people within the organization. The organization chosen as a case study is a private university type.

We can admit that there are several types of manifest entropies at different organizational levels. The accumulation of these various types of entropies has as an inevitable effect the destructuring of that organization or in other cases, its reorganization. These issues are applicable especially in the mountain regions. (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h)

The need to study this topic started from the scientific curiosity triggered by the unscientific observation of the university organizational environment and how it adjusts to internal and external challenges. Their own scientific need to understand and objectify the elements of organizational culture that keep the organization in the area of survival or even develop it along with the academic curiosity of the processes within the organization have shaped this approach.

Objective:

The primary objective is to discern the ways in which organizational culture acts as a stabilizing force, enabling private universities to not only withstand entropic pressures but also to thrive and adapt in the face of adversity.

Findings:

Preliminary findings suggest that a well-defined organizational culture contributes significantly to the resilience of private universities. Values that promote adaptability, innovation, and a collaborative atmosphere act as countermeasures to entropic challenges.

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Methodology:

This research adopts a qualitative approach, drawing on extensive observations within a private university setting. Interviews with key organizational figures, document analyses, and participant observations contribute to the holistic understanding of how organizational culture serves as a buffer against entropic disruptions.

Issue reshapes:

In the ever-changing landscape of organizational dynamics, this paper embarks on a mountain research expedition to scrutinize how organizations, particularly private universities, navigate and endure in the face of strong entropic forces. The focal point of our investigation lies in understanding the pivotal role organizational culture plays in mitigating the impact of entropy on the structure and functionality of these institutions. This exploration encapsulates the values embraced, operational methodologies employed, and the overall ethos fostered among individuals within the organization.

Considering the multifaceted nature of entropic manifestations across diverse organizational levels, we posit that a confluence of entropic influences could lead to either the disintegration or, conversely, the reformation of an organization. Our case study revolves around a private university, offering a contextual lens to examine the entropic challenges it encounters and how its organizational culture serves as a mechanism for resilience and adaptation.

The impetus for this research stems from a blend of scientific curiosity and unstructured observations of the university organizational environment. Our scientific pursuit is driven by the imperative to comprehend and objectify the elements of organizational culture that anchor an institution within the realm of survival or catalyze its growth. Concurrently, an academic curiosity fuels our desire to delve into the intricate processes unfolding within the organization, shedding light on how it responds to internal and external challenges.

Organizations, particularly those in the academic sphere, are subject to a myriad of entropic forces that continuously shape and reshape their structures. This paper seeks to undertake a comprehensive exploration, akin to ascending a metaphorical mountain, to unravel the intricate dynamics of how private universities navigate through entropic challenges. The chosen focus is on organizational culture, encompassing the shared values, methodologies, and atmosphere within the academic institution.

Results:

The investigation into the role of organizational culture in private universities grappling with strong entropic forces has yielded preliminary findings that shed light on crucial aspects of their resilience and adaptive strategies.

The qualitative approach employed in this research involved in-depth interviews with key organizational figures, meticulous document analyses, and keen participant observations within the unique context of a private university. The exploration of organizational culture, encompassing values, operational methodologies, and the overall ethos among individuals, provided valuable insights into how these elements serve as a buffer against entropic disruptions.

The preliminary findings underscore the significance of a well-defined organizational culture in enhancing the resilience of private universities. The identified values, such as adaptability, innovation, and a collaborative atmosphere, emerged as effective countermeasures to the entropic challenges that organizations face. These cultural attributes act as stabilizing forces, enabling private universities not only to withstand entropic pressures but also to thrive and adapt in the face of adversity.

The multifaceted nature of entropic manifestations across diverse organizational levels was evident in the case study, indicating that a confluence of entropic influences could lead to either the disintegration or reformation of an organization. The private university under scrutiny showcased the dynamic interplay between its organizational culture and the entropic challenges encountered, highlighting the adaptability and resilience fostered within its unique context.

In conclusion, the preliminary findings suggest a compelling relationship between organizational culture and the ability of private universities to navigate entropic challenges. As we metaphorically ascend the mountain of organizational survival, this research contributes nuanced understandings that extend beyond academic discourse. The identified cultural attributes provide practical insights for organizations, illuminating strategies for not only surviving but thriving in the ever-changing landscape of entropic forces.

Conclusion:

As we ascend the metaphorical mountain of organizational survival, this research endeavors to provide a nuanced understanding of how private universities, through the prism of their organizational culture, navigate and endure in the entropic context. By shedding light on the intricacies of this dynamic relationship, the findings aim to contribute not only to academic discourse but also to the practical strategies employed by organizations facing entropic challenges.

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